

Evaluation of True Electrophoretic Mobility of Protein-coated Glass Particles by Microcataphoretic Method

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The observed electrophoretic mobility of Bovine Serum Albumin (B.S.A.)*-coated pyrex glass is found to be a function of the size of the particles. A plot of the reciprocal of radii of the particles against the reciprocal of their observed mobilities exhibits a linear relationship provided that the values of kr (k is the reciprocal of the Debye-Hückel distance and r is the radius of the particle) are sufficiently large. From the intercepts of the straight lines for different values of pH , the true electrophoretic mobilities of protein-coated glass particles have been evaluated. The variation of mobility with the radius of the particles indicates definitely that glass particles, coated with B. S. A., possess appreciable surface conductance.

A close agreement between the electric mobility of dissolved protein molecules and the mobility of microscopically visible particles, covered with an adsorbed film of the same protein, has been reported by many authors¹. Therefore the conclusion has been drawn that the mobility of a particle, covered with an adsorbed protein, is characteristic of the adsorbed substance. On the other hand, many authors believe that the nature of the underlying surface also influences considerably the mobility of the adsorbed substances. Recently Bull and Chatteraj² have shown that the mobilities of B. S. A.-coated particles of paraffin, nujol, and pyrex glass at the same pH and protein concentration exhibit considerable divergence in experimental values. Abramson³ noticed that quartz particles, coated with egg albumin and serum albumin, had mobilities identical with that of the molecules of the respective proteins. Nevertheless, there are instances where adsorption causes a difference in mobilities and a shift of the isoelectric point, although the pH -mobility curve retains its characteristic shape. The variation in mobility in the adsorbed state has been explained by Bull⁴ on the assumption that the radius of curvature is characteristic of the absorbent and the charge density, that of the adsorbate. Bull has also demonstrated that the mobility of B. S. A. and ovalbumin, adsorbed on pyrex glass, varies with ionic strength.

The electrophoretic equation of Henry⁵ can be written as:

$$\bar{U} = \frac{DX\zeta}{8\pi\eta} [1 + \lambda' \{3f(kr) - 2\}] \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{U}$ represents the electrophoretic velocity, X , the potential gradient, with $\lambda' = \frac{Sr - 2\kappa}{2Sr + 2\kappa}$ where κ is the specific surface conductance and S , the specific conductance in bulk of the solution of the electrolyte; $f(kr)$ represents a function of (kr) .

*The B. S. A. was supplied by Pentex Biochemicals, Illinois, U.S.A.

1. Abramson, Moyer and Gorn, "Electrophoresis of Proteins and Chemistry of Cell Surfaces", Reinhold, New York, 1942.
2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 5128.
3. *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1932, **15**, 575.
4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 1901.
5. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, **44**, 1022.

For sufficiently large values of kr , Ghosh and co-workers^{6,7} have shown that equation (1) can be expressed in the form:

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + \frac{\chi}{\zeta \cdot r \cdot S} \quad \dots \dots \quad (2)$$

where ζ_a denotes the value of zeta-potential based on Smoluchowski's equation and ζ , its true value.

Equation (2) can also be written as

$$\frac{1}{U_a} = \frac{1}{U} + \frac{\chi}{U \cdot r \cdot S} \quad \dots \dots \quad (3)$$

where U_a and U are the observed (*i. e.*, experimental) and the true electrophoretic mobilities respectively of the particles. Under the condition in which χ , U , and S remain constant, equation (3) can be written as

$$\frac{1}{U_a} = \frac{1}{U} + \frac{m}{r} \quad \dots \dots \quad (4)$$

where $m = \chi/U \cdot S =$ a constant.

For a given concentration of electrolyte, S , χ , and U should remain constant. Therefore for particles having different values of ' r ', U_a will be different and according to equation (4) a plot of $1/U_a$ against $1/r$ should give a straight line. Experiments have therefore been undertaken with protein-coated particles (*a*) to ascertain if such particles show appreciable surface conductance and (*b*) to follow equation (4).

EXPERIMENTAL

Samples of pyrex glass particles of different sizes were prepared by fractional sedimentation from their suspension in water. Five samples, each having particle of radius different from that of the other, were prepared and the average radius of the particles of each sample was found from the measurement of rate of sedimentation.

Solutions (0.02% and 0.1%) of crystalline and dialysed B. S. A. having different pH's were prepared. The ionic strength of these solution was maintained at 0.0004 by adjusting the proportion of HCl and NaCl.

Samples of pyrex glass particles were treated separately in different bottles with these solutions and shaken vigorously so that the particles were coated with the protein. Electrophoretic mobilities of these protein-coated particles were determined in a microcataphoretic apparatus at 25°.

The microcataphoretic cell used by us was the Abramson modification of the original Northrop-Kunitz type flat cell, it being oriented laterally. Adopting this orientation, one can determine the electrophoretic component of velocity of a particle directly and ignore

6. Ghosh *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 29.

7. Ghosh and Roy, *Nature*, 1955, 176, 1080.

the component in the perpendicular direction due to settling or convection. This type of orientation of the cell was first suggested by Hartman *et al.*⁸ and subsequently employed by Bull⁴.

Since the protein-coated glass particles have low mobility, a high field is often necessary to produce an appreciable movement of the particles. This was achieved by using an electrical power source in the circuit. The microscope with which the particles were observed in the cell carried a micrometer scale in the eye piece. In each sample, the particle size was found to vary within narrow limits. With the help of the micrometer scale, it is easy, however, to select particles of the desired size and measure their mobilities in the applied electric field.

DISCUSSION

Figs. 1-3 show the plot of the reciprocal of the observed electrophoretic mobilities of protein-coated pyrex glass particles against the reciprocal of the radii of the particles at different values of pH and protein concentration. It will be noticed that there exists a linear relationship down to particles of radius 2.1 microns as required by equation (4). True electrophoretic mobility, U , has been evaluated from the intercept and m has been calculated from the slope of the linear plot (represented by lines in Figs. 1-3). For particles of radius 1.6 microns, the values of $1/U_a$ fall below the straight lines. This deviation should be attributed to the fact that kr is no longer sufficiently large for the system (kr being equal to 104 for the system) and hence the assumption that $f(kr)$ is unity does not hold.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

True electrophoretic mobilities of pyrex-glass particles, coated with protein (B. S. A.) at different pH's, have been evaluated from the corresponding intercepts of the graphs represented by Figs. 1-3. It may be noticed that the true electrophoretic mobility of B. S. A.-coated pyrex glass particles at protein concentrations of 0.02% and 0.1% remains almost the same at a particular pH of the solution.

True ζ -potential has been calculated from true electrophoretic mobility obtained in the way discussed above and α has been calculated from the relation $\alpha = m.U.S$. The value of $\{3f(kr) - 2\}$ has been found from Henry's standard curves³ for different values of kr . Thus knowing the values of true ζ , α , and $\{3f(kr) - 2\}$, U_a has been calculated by using

Henry's equation (1) for different values of r . Fig. 4 shows the variation of U_a with kr . In Fig. 4 the points represent the experimental data and the dotted lines represent the values of U_a found from Henry's equation. It will be noticed that the agreement is fairly satisfactory.

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

The variation of U_a with the radius of the particles definitely indicates that glass particles, coated with pure B. S. A., possess appreciable surface conductance, especially when the specific conductance of the intermicellar solution is low. This observation is significant in view of the general belief that the true ζ -potential of protein-coated particles can be found from their electrophoretic velocity by using the Smoluchowski equation without applying any correction.

The isoelectric point of B. S. A. at ionic strength 0.0004 with protein concentration of 0.02% has been found to be 5.1 from a curve (Fig. 5) obtained by plotting the true electrophoretic mobilities of protein-coated particles at different ρ^H 's. Bull⁴ has recently shown that isoelectric point of B. S. A., adsorbed on pyrex glass, varies linearly with the square root of ionic strength. From the extrapolation of the curve, obtained by him, the isoelectric point of B. S. A. at ionic strength 0.0004 has been found to be 5.06, which is in satisfactory agreement with the value 5.10 obtained by the present workers.